

AREAL DIFFERENTIATION OF VERB SUFFIXES IN THE DISTRICTS OF KUGAY VILLAGE

Turdiyeva Ma'mura Hasanboy qizi

Independent researcher

turdiyevamamura7@gmail.com

Ne'matova Surayyo Nodirjon qizi

Assistant professor at Tashkent State University
of Uzbek Language and Literature

nsurayyo1812@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the morphological features characteristic of the dialect of the village of Kogai in the Uchkurgan district, which is one of the dialects of the Namangan dialectal zone.

Today, the development of science in our country is progressing significantly. Most importantly, every theoretical knowledge is being strengthened and developed through practice. The field of dialectology, which forms the basis of our literary language and is the most important branch of linguistics, is no exception. The fundamental goal of dialectology is to study specific dialects, which are the inner source of national spirituality, enlightenment, and development, to restore their complete lexical base, and to analyze this lexical content. In his speech at the ceremonial meeting dedicated to the 30th anniversary of granting the Uzbek language the status of state language, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about the need to increase the effectiveness and radically improve the quality of scientific research related to the peculiarities of the Uzbek language, its dialects, historical development, and prospects. [lex.uz]

Based on this, the comprehensive study of Uzbek folk dialects and vernaculars, which are considered unique sources for the development of the Uzbek literary language with its rich lexical reserve, is becoming one of the requirements of our time. Today's global development, the rapprochement of states and peoples, and integration are creating new approaches to this issue. One of these is the study of dialectological research from an aerial, that is, territorial aspect.

Among the world's languages, Uzbek dialects stand out for their diversity, being influenced by Arabic, Persian, Russian and other languages. This process has left a big mark on Uzbek dialects. One of these regions is the Namangan region.

Studying Namangan dialects from an aerial perspective can yield great scientific results for linguistics. It should be noted that the goal of areal linguistics is to study the territorial characteristics of languages and dialects, that is, to cover a specific language area frontally, to study the interaction of the widespread and dominant language in this area with the languages in contact, to determine the dialectal zones of the languages in the language array,

and to scientifically interpret the characteristics of the base dialect in the zone and its relationship with the surrounding (peripheral) languages and dialects. [Ashirboev: 2021, 5]

The Kogai area, which is considered the object of our research, is located in the northeastern part of the Uchkurgan district of the Namangan region. Currently, the village of Kogai is divided into 6 sections, which are named as follows: Section 1. Uchyogoch. Section 2. Uchkuprik. Section 3. Pakhtachi. Section 4. Kurgancha. Section 5. Birlik. Section 6. Sample.

Of these sections, Uchyogoch and Namuna (sections 1 and 6) are located near the central part of the village of Qogai. This can be seen from the map below. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Map of the village of Qo'g'ai.

The

remaining sections, namely the sections known as Uchko'prik, Pakhtachi, Kurgancha, and Birlik, are located further away from the village center. Let's look at the map. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Map of the border areas of the village of Qo'g'ai.

As can be seen from the map, some sections are located very close to the village center, while others are situated farther away. During the research process, certain morphological similarities and differences were observed in the dialects of the population living in these sections. These are especially noticeable in acoustic changes in the present and future tense verb suffixes, and sometimes in past tense suffixes. For example, the inhabitants of the first, third, fourth, fifth, and sixth sections of the village use the present tense suffix -yapti, while the inhabitants of the second section pronounce it as -vetty. For instance: [kevetty] (is coming), [yevvetty] (is eating), [uxlevetty] (is sleeping), [yetvetty] (is reaching), [o'qivetty] (is reading), [gar'rvetty] (is speaking), [yozvetty] (is writing), [eshitvetty] (is hearing), [ko'rvetty] (is seeing), [ko'nvetty] (is agreeing), [tikvetty] (is sewing), [sanch'lvetty] (is being pricked), [tarbyelevetty] (is raising/educating). Additionally, when the negative form suffix -ma of the verb is added to the suffix -vetty, which is used instead of the present tense suffix -yapti, it is pronounced as -mevetty. For example: [kemevetty] (is not coming), [yemevetty] (is not eating), [uxlemevetty] (is not sleeping), [yetmevetty] (is not reaching).

In these words, we can observe another phenomenon: the suffix -vetty changes the sounds that precede it. For example, it changes the sound 'a' in the suffix -ma to the sound 'e'. We have examined this based on the above examples, but we can also observe another interesting phenomenon. The -me in the dialect causes changes in the sounds of the preceding suffixes as well. For instance, if we write the word tarbiyalamayapti as [tarbyelemevetty] based on the dialect, it becomes easier to analyze it phonetically. We can see that [vetty] strongly influences the sound [a] in the preceding negative form [-ma], changing it to [e]. This suffix, in turn, strongly affects the sound [a] in the preceding verb-forming suffix [-la], also changing it to [e]. Isogloss is one of the important concepts in areal linguistics. This word comes from Latin, with "iso" meaning "equal" and "glossa" meaning "language," and it is a conventional sign indicating the distribution of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical features within a dialect or related languages according to their degree of correspondence. In other words, it is a conventional sign used to mark the distribution lines of language and dialect features on

linguistic maps and to represent each linguistic feature. This term was introduced to science by the Latvian dialectologist A. Bielenstein. The term isogloss expresses the following meaning: an isogloss indicates the attribute of a linguistic area in mapping. In this case, each isogloss is displayed on the map and its distribution width is shown. In this width, the denser placement of isoglosses can indicate an older range of the language or dialect phenomenon or its firm establishment in the area, while more sparsely located isoglosses can suggest that it emerged later or leads to the native range. [Ashirboev: 2023, 38]

In the rural sections, we will focus on the following isomorphemes and isophones:

We have observed the use of the third-person personal-number suffix [-lar], which expresses respect, in the second, third, and fourth sections. It is noteworthy that the isomorpheme [-lar] is actively used as the isomorpheme [-lə]. In the third and fourth sections, this isophoneme is used as follows: Dadamlar, onamlar, opamlar, ukamlar, ular, etc. In the second section, it appears as: Dədomlə, onamlə, opamlə, ukamlə, ulə, etc.

Additionally, the future tense suffix -a is pronounced differently across these sections. For example, in the 2nd section, qile:rədi [qilaveradi], bo'le:rədi [bo'laveradi]. In the dialect of Section 6, the future tense suffix -a is pronounced as a long 'o': Qilo':radi [qilaveradi], bo':lovradi [bo'laveradi].

As can be seen, the sound -a results in an isophoneme due to its varying pronunciation in different regions.

The variants of the present-future participle -vg'ich// -ɔvg'ich// -uvg'ɨch are mainly found in older people. However, they are not present in the dialects of people born in the recent past. The ancestors of those who speak such dialects are primarily related to speakers of the Kipchak dialect. In phrases such as [bɔrg'ɔn yəhmɔn//bɔrg'ɔn yəhsɔn] borganim yo'q//borganing yo'q, [qig'ɔn yəhmɔn//qig'ɔn yəhsɔn] qilganim yo'q//qilganing yo'q, [kɔrgən yəhmɔn//kɔrgən yəhsɔn] ko'rganim yo'q, ko'rganing yo'q, [ɔg'ɔn yəhmɔn//ɔg'ɔn yəhsɔn] olganim yo'q, olganing yo'q, the consonant q of the word yo'q is pronounced as x/h. In this case, we can primarily observe that a phonetic change has occurred.

Analysis specific to the Qo'g'ay dialect shows that from a morphological perspective, the phonetic phenomena in the affixes of this tense arise from the simplification of pronunciation in both native and borrowed words, and the adaptation of the dialect to the norms of its internal phonetic-phonological and orthoepic laws. Our language has long been distinguished from other languages by its wealth of dialects and vernaculars. Each dialect has its own grammatical features, including phonetic, lexical, and morphological characteristics. Due to these features, dialects differ from one another. [Darvishev: 2019, 148]

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